

On Van, R and S Topological Characteristics of Polyphenylene Dendrimers

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ABSTRACT

Hyperbranched monodisperse macromolecules with persistent shape and constrained size are called dendrimers. Topological indices are numerical parameters that relate the molecular structure's chemical, physical, and biological characteristics. We calculated the novel R, S, and Van molecular topological indices of polyphenylene dendrimer, which are degree-based molecular descriptors. Our findings contribute to a deeper comprehension of the characteristics of polyphenylene dendrimer that can be employed in medication development.

Keywords: Polyphenylene dendrimer; R index, S index, Van index

Introduction

In recent years, a lot of new medications for many different disorders have been found. Before it is produced, its characteristics, toxicity level, and behavioral patterns must be researched.

These medications require a lot of time and money to experiment with in industry. The biological, physicochemical, and therapeutic aspects of chemical structures are provided by graph theoretical notions. Therefore, topological indices can be utilized to describe these medications' characteristics. Topological indices are numerical values that describe a chemical compound's molecular structure. It is invariant under graph automorphism and aids in the analysis of the physicochemical and biological properties of the chemical substance. The quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR) and quantitative

structure-activity relationships (QSAR) of chemical compounds, which provide the correlation properties of chemical compounds, are analyzed using the topological indices [1–3]. It is unavoidable in the fields of chemistry and pharmacology, particularly for drug design, due to their significant involvement in QSPR and QSAR research. Utilizing molecular descriptors, the effects and behavior of chemical structures are examined. Topological indices are used to study the characteristics of networks [4–9]. Utilizing topological indices, the characteristics of dendrimers have recently been the subject of extensive research [10–19].

One of the key components of the rapidly developing field of nano-biotechnology, which uses nano-fabrication's tools and techniques to create devices for investigating biosystems, is the dendrimer. Dendrimers are macromolecules with repeated branches that have received a lot of theoretical and experimental attention. Hyperbranched macromolecules known as dendrimers are radially symmetric, include increasing branches surrounding the central region, and are hyperbranched [20,21]. A centre core with functional features, branches that expand with each generation, and a terminal portion with functional/peripheral groups make up the structure. The hyperbranching architectures and iterative production of dendrimers set them apart from other common polymers [22]. It has a three-dimensional architecture with a high dendrimer functionality and a low polydispersity [23,24]. Dendrimers are a good drug delivery vehicle due to their mono-dispersity, polyvalency, self-assembly, stability, electrostatic interactions, and unimolecular micelles [20,25]. As a result, it can be used as carriers in anticancer medications and nanomedicines for drug delivery. Due of dendrimers' great functionality, they are used in biological applications [26]. It is essential to the system for delivering genes [27]. Despite having a wide range of applications in biology and medicine, it is restricted by its toxicity [28–30].

PPDs, which are monodisperse three-dimensional macromolecules, are nanostructures that resemble those seen in nature [31]. These dendrimers, produced through organic synthesis, have biological applications. They maintain their size and shape throughout time [32]. PPD comprises three sections, similar to dendrimers, where the functions can be tailored. This characteristic has led to a number of applications in the field of organic electronics, including weakly coordinating cations and anion [33]. PPDs have a low level of toxicity, a high level of cell absorption, and can transport therapeutic medicines across cell membranes [32].

The degree-based R, S and Van topological indices of the polyphenylene dendrimer $D_4[n]$ are calculated in this article.

2. Preliminaries

Let G be a chemical graph and v a vertex(atom) of G . The degree of vertex v , denoted as $\deg(v)$, is the total number of edges which is incident to v . $N(v)$ is the set of all neighbouring vertices of v . The sum degree of the vertex v , denoted as S_v , is the total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . The multiplication degree of the vertex v , denoted as M_v , is the multiplication of total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . Van degree of the vertex v , defined as; $van(v) = \frac{S_v}{M_v}$ [34].

Also, reverse Van degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rvan(v) = \frac{M_v}{S_v}$. Van topological indices defined as [34];

The first Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} van(v)^2$.

The second Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$.

The third Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [van(u) + van(v)]$.

The first reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rvan(v)^2$.

The second reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$.

The third reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rvan(u) + rvan(v)]$.

R degree of the vertex v , defined as; $r(v) = M_v + S_v$ [35]. Also, reverse R degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rr(v) = \frac{1}{M_v + S_v}$. R topological indices defined as [35]:

The first R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} r(v)^2$.

The second R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$.

The third R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [r(u) + r(v)]$.

The first reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rr(v)^2$.

The second reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$.

The third reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rr(u) + rr(v)]$.

S degree of the vertex v , defined as; $s(v) = |M_v - S_v|$ [36]. Also, reverse S degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rs(v) = \frac{1}{|M_v - S_v| + 1}$. R topological indices defined as [36]:

The first S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} s(v)^2$.

The second S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$.

The third S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [s(u) + s(v)]$.

The first reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rs(v)^2$.

The second reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$.

The third reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rs(u) + rs(v)]$.

Figure 1. An illustration of polyphenylene dendrimer $D_4[n]$ with two development stages

3. Polyphenylene dendrimer

There are $140 \times 2^n - 112$ edges and $120 \times 2^n - 95$ vertices in the polyphenylene dendrimer, $D_4[n]$. The graph of polyphenylene dendrimers $D_4[n]$ of generations G2 with two development stages is displayed in Figure 1. Polyphenylene dendrimer, $D_4[n]$ has the following sum and multiplication edge vertex degree partitions which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Edge vertex sum and multiplication degree partition of Polyphenylene dendrimer, $D_4[n]$

Cardinality	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)	Cardinality	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)
$24 \times 2^n - 16$	(4,4)	(4,4)	2	(7,7)	(12,12)
$24 \times 2^n - 16$	(4,5)	(4,6)	$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(7,8)	(12,18)
$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(5,5)	(6,6)	$12 \times 2^n - 12$	(7,9)	(12,27)
$40 \times 2^n - 32$	(5,7)	(6,12)	$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(8,9)	(18,27)

$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(6,8)	(8,18)	$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(9,9)	(27,27)
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With the help of Table 1, the Van, R and S edge vertex degree partitions of Polyphenylene dendrimer, $D_4[n]$ are given in Table 2.

Table 2 Van, R and S edge vertex degree partitions Polyphenylene dendrimer, $D_4[n]$

Cardinality	$(van(u), van(v))$	$(rvan(u), rvan(v))$	$(r(u), r(v))$	$(rr(u), rr(v))$	$(s(u), s(v))$	$(rs(u), rs(v))$
$24 \times 2^n - 16$	(1,1)	(1,1)	(8,8)	(1/8,1/8)	(0,0)	(1,1)
$24 \times 2^n - 16$	(1,2/3)	(1,3/2)	(8,11)	(1/8,1/11)	(0,1)	(1,1/2)
$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(5/6,5/6)	(6/5,6/5)	(11,11)	(1/11,1/11)	(1,1)	(1/2,1/2)
$40 \times 2^n - 32$	(5/6,7/12)	(6/5,12/7)	(11,19)	(1/11,1/19)	(1,5)	(1/2,1/6)
$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(3/4,2/9)	(4/3,9/2)	(14,26)	(1/14,1/26)	(2,10)	(1/3,1/11)
2	(7/12,7/12)	(12/7,12/7)	(19,19)	(1/19,1/19)	(5,5)	(1/6,1/6)
$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(7/12,4/9)	(12/7,9/4)	(19,26)	(1/19,1/26)	(5,10)	(1/6,1/11)
$12 \times 2^n - 12$	(7/12,1/3)	(12/7,3)	(19,36)	(1/19,1/36)	(5,22)	(1/6,1/23)
$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(4/9,1/3)	(9/4,3)	(26,36)	(1/26,1/36)	(10,18)	(1/11,1/19)
$8 \times 2^n - 8$	(1/3,1/3)	(3,3)	(36,36)	(1/36,1/36)	(18,18)	(1/19,1/19)

The following theorems give the overall Van, R, and S indices representation of polyphenylene dendrimer, $D_4[n]$:

Theorem 1. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the second Van index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Van^2(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{5}{3} \\
 &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{113}{108} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{35}{72} \\
 &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{7}{36} + \frac{49}{72}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$Van^2(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} van(u)van(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^2(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 1 \times 1 + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 1 \times \frac{2}{3} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{5}{6} \times \frac{5}{6} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{5}{6} \times \frac{7}{12} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{3}{4} \times \frac{2}{9} \\ &+ 2 \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{7}{12} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{4}{9} + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{1}{3} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{4}{9} \times \frac{1}{3} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{1}{3} \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 2. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the second reverse Van index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^{2r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{5}{2} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{18933}{700} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{72}{35} + \\ &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{36}{7} + \frac{288}{49} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$Van^{2r}(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} rvan(u)rvan(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^{2r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 1 \times 1 + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 1 \times \frac{3}{2} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{6}{5} \times \frac{6}{5} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{6}{5} \times \frac{12}{7} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{4}{3} \times \frac{9}{2} \\ &+ 2 \times \frac{12}{7} \times \frac{12}{7} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{12}{7} \times \frac{9}{4} + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{12}{7} \times 3 \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{9}{4} \times 3 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 3 \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 3. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the third Van index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$Van^3(D_4[n]) = (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{11}{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{46}{27} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{17}{12} \\
 &\quad + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{11}{12} + \frac{7}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$Van^3(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} (van(u) + van(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Van^3(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (1 + 1) + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \left(1 + \frac{2}{3}\right) \\
 &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{5}{6}\right) + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{3}{4} + \frac{2}{9}\right) \\
 &+ 2 \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{4}{9}\right) + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{1}{3}\right) \\
 &\quad + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{4}{9} + \frac{1}{3}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 4. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the third reverse Van index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Van^{3r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{9}{2} \\
 &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{8119}{210} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{102}{35} \\
 &\quad + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{33}{7} + \frac{48}{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$Van^{3r}(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} (rvan(u) + rvan(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Van^{3r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (1 + 1) + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \left(1 + \frac{3}{2}\right) \\
 &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{6}{5} + \frac{6}{5}\right) + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \left(\frac{6}{5} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{4}{3} + \frac{9}{2}\right) \\
 &+ 2 \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + \frac{9}{4}\right) + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + 3\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{9}{4} + 3\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (3 + 3)$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 5. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the second R index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} R^2(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 152 \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 4291 + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times 209 \\ &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times 684 + 722 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$R^2(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} r(u)r(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} R^2(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 8 \times 8 + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 8 \times 11 \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 11 \times 11 + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times 11 \times 19 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 14 \times 26 \\ &+ 2 \times 19 \times 19 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 19 \times 26 + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times 19 \times 36 \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 26 \times 36 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 36 \times 36 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 6. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the second reverse R index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} R^{2r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{19}{704} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{908773}{6892776} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{1}{209} + \\ &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{1}{684} + \frac{2}{361} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$R^{2r}(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} r_{van}(u)r_{van}(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$R^{2r}(D_4[n]) = (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{1}{8} \times \frac{1}{8} + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{1}{8} \times \frac{1}{11}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{11} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{19} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{14} \times \frac{1}{26} \\
 &+ 2 \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{19} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{26} + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{36} \\
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{26} \times \frac{1}{36} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{36} \times \frac{1}{36}
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 7. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the third R index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 R^3(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 35 \\
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 241 + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times 30 \\
 &+(12 \times 2^n - 12) \times 55 + 76
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$R^3(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} (r(u) + r(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned}
 R^3(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (8 + 8) + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (8 + 11) \\
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (11 + 11) + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times (11 + 19) \\
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (14 + 26) \\
 &+ 2 \times (19 + 19) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (19 + 26) + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times (19 + 36) \\
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (26 + 36) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (36 + 36)
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 8. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the third reverse Van index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 R^{3r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{41}{88} \\
 &+(8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{3109401}{6162156} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{30}{209} + \\
 &+(12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{55}{684} + \frac{4}{19}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$R^{3r}(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} (rr(u) + rr(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} R^{3r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \left(\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8}\right) + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \left(\frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{11}\right) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{19}\right) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{14} + \frac{1}{26}\right) \\ &+ 2 \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{19}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{26}\right) + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{36}\right) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{26} + \frac{1}{36}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{36} + \frac{1}{36}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 9. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the second S index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} S^2(D_4[n]) &= (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 575 + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times 5 \\ &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times 110 + 50 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$S^2(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} s(u)s(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} S^2(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 0 \times 0 + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 0 \times 1 \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 1 \times 1 + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times 1 \times 5 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 2 \times 10 \\ &+ 2 \times 5 \times 5 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 5 \times 10 + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times 5 \times 22 \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 10 \times 18 + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 18 \times 18 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 10. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the second reverse S index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} S^{2r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{3}{2} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{4813}{15884} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{1}{12} \\ &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{1}{138} + \frac{1}{18} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$S^{2r}(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} rs(u)rs(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} S^{2r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 1 \times 1 + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times 1 \times \frac{1}{2} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{6} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{3} \times \frac{1}{11} \\ &+ 2 \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{6} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{11} + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{23} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{19} + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{19} \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 11. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the third S index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} S^3(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times 83 + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times 6 \\ &+ (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times 27 + 20 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$S^3(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} (s(u) + s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} S^3(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (0 + 0) + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (0 + 1) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (1 + 1) + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times (1 + 5) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (2 + 10) \\ &+ 2 \times (5 + 5) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (5 + 10) + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times (5 + 22) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (10 + 18) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times (18 + 18) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 12. Let $D_4[n]$ be a polyphenylene dendrimer network. Then, the third reverse S index of $D_4[n]$ is;

$$\begin{aligned} S^{3r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \frac{5}{2} \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \frac{7588}{3135} + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \frac{2}{3} \end{aligned}$$

$$+(12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \frac{29}{138} + \frac{2}{3}$$

Proof. Considering that $D_4[n]$ is a polyphenylene dendrimer network. By definition;

$$S^{3r}(D_4[n]) = \sum_{uv \in E(D_4[n])} (rs(u) + rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} S^{3r}(D_4[n]) &= (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times (1 + 1) + (24 \times 2^n - 16) \times \left(1 + \frac{1}{2}\right) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right) + (40 \times 2^n - 32) \times \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{11}\right) \\ &+ 2 \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + (12 \times 2^n - 12) \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{23}\right) \\ &+ (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{19}\right) + (8 \times 2^n - 8) \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{19}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

4. Results and discussion

Tables 3,4 and 5 give the numerical findings from $D_4[2]n$'s S, R, Van topological indices. We can see trends and effects on the molecule structure by plotting the $D_4[2]$ molecular descriptors. We have provided a graphical illustration, see Figure 2.

Table 3. Numerical values of Van indices from $n = 1$ to $n = 8$.

n	$Van^2(D_4[n])$	$Van^{2r}(D_4[n])$	$Van^3(D_4[n])$	$Van^{3r}(D_4[n])$
1	88,050	462,711	212,296	656,609
2	228,347	1303,466	550,888	1837,485
3	523,809	2984,974	1228,074	4199,238
4	1070,125	6347,991	2582,444	8922,742
5	2192,495	13074,026	5291,185	18369,752
6	4437,236	26526,094	10708,666	37263,771
7	8926,717	53430,231	21543,629	75051,809
8	17905,680	107238,506	43213,555	150627,885

Table 4. Numerical values of R indices from n = 1 to n= 8.

n	$R^2(D_4[n])$	$R^{2r}(D_4[n])$	$R^3(D_4[n])$	$R^{3r}(D_4[n])$
1	58154	58154	5224	27,011
2	167242	167242	14480	70,861
3	385418	385418	32992	158,562
4	821770	821770	70016	333,963
5	1694474	1694474	144064	684,765
6	3439882	3439882	292160	1386,369
7	6930698	6930698	588352	2789,577
8	13912330	13912330	1180736	5595,993

Table 5. Numerical values of S indices from n = 1 to n= 8.

n	$S^2(D_4[n])$	$S^{2r}(D_4[n])$	$S^3(D_4[n])$	$S^{3r}(D_4[n])$
1	6210	54,566	1328	134,551
2	18450	138,255	3832	351,655
3	42930	305,632	8840	785,862
4	91890	640,387	18856	1654,275
5	189810	1309,897	38888	3391,103
6	385650	2770,572	78952	6864,758
7	777330	5326,956	159080	13812,068
8	1560690	10683,035	319336	27706,689

Figure 2 Topological indices of $D_4[n]$

5. Conclusion

The investigation of QSAR (Quantitative Structure-Activity Relation)/QSPR (Quantitative Structure-Property Relation)/QSTR (Quantitative Structure-Toxicology Relation) activities is aided by the formulation of numerical expressions. Scientists may be able to assess a substance's activity in drug design by examining its toxicity, solubility, and size, which has several uses in the field of nanomedicine as a drug delivery vehicle. We calculated the R, S, and Van molecular topological indices of polyphenylene dendrimer, which are degree-based molecular descriptors. Our findings contribute to a deeper comprehension of the characteristics of polyphenylene dendrimer that can be employed in medication development.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author.

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